

Schools as Ethical Decision-Makers—Educational Ethics at the Meso-Level

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Introduction

Education and ethics are intrinsically intertwined, with the very interpretation of “education” being an inherently ethical endeavor. Our definitions of education are shaped by normative conceptions of what it means to be human—conceptions that, in turn, inform our educational aims and practices (e.g., Dewey, 1909; Jäger, 1934, p. 24; Nida-Rümelin, 2013, p. 21; Pieper, 2017, p. 129). This relationship is particularly evident within formal education, where teaching, learning, and training are organized and carried out within the framework of established educational systems (Rohlf, 2011).

Schools are far more than places for acquiring facts and passing tests. They are dynamic environments that influence and are influenced by cultural, social, political, and ethical considerations (Dewey, 1909, part I). The underlying philosophy of education rests on a fundamental ethical foundation, which profoundly influences and shapes our understanding of the true purpose of schooling. Hence, different perspectives offer distinct views on the role of schools in shaping individuals and society, as illustrated by the following examples.

According to *essentialism* (e.g., William C. Bagley, 1934), schools should focus on teaching essential academic subjects to prepare students for life and citizenship, emphasizing core knowledge and skills. In contrast, *progressivism* (e.g., John Dewey, 1916) advocates hands-on, problem-solving learning environments that foster critical thinking, creativity, and social responsibility. *Perennialism* (e.g., Robert Hutchins, 1952) argues that education should focus on enduring truths and classical works to cultivate intellectual rigor and understanding of fundamental ideas. Meanwhile, *reconstructionism* (e.g., George Counts, 1932) views schools as instruments of social change, urging education to address societal issues and prepare students to contribute to justice and progress. *Existentialism* (inspired by Jean-Paul Sartre, 1946) emphasizes personal freedom and self-creation, encouraging students to explore their identity and meaning in life, while *critical pedagogy* (e.g., Paulo Freire, 1970) seeks to challenge power structures, promote social justice, and empower students through dialogue and active engagement with societal norms. Given their normative perspective on what schools *should* or *ought to* pursue, it is evident that the approaches outlined above are fundamentally ethical in nature.

Education systems involve numerous actors who each bear significant responsibility for their decisions. These decisions are not only administrative or logistical in nature, but often involve deeply ethical considerations, particularly when it comes to children and adolescents—groups

whose life trajectories are profoundly shaped by the choices made within their educational journey (Fend, 2008a, 2008b; Brumlik, 2017). Ethical decisions in the context of formal education span across various levels, from the overarching policies set at the national level to the autonomous choices made within individual schools, and down to the day-to-day decisions made by teachers within the classroom. In every instance, stakeholders are tasked to make judgments that have the potential to impact not only the present but also the future of those in their care.

Historically, in the Western world, the connection between formal education (as well as pedagogy in general) and ethics was considered self-evident, from antiquity through the Middle Ages and into modern times (Horster & Oelkers, 2005, p. 7). However, in the 20th century, this relationship began to fade from the foreground, receiving less attention in educational discourse (Wigger, 1998, p. 193; cited in Prengel, 2020, p. 48). Despite this shift, ethical questions within the educational and schooling context have continued to be explored, albeit in more fragmented ways. However, in the broader philosophical field of applied ethics, educational ethics has often occupied a marginal position, rarely addressed in standard works on the subject, and remaining an almost invisible presence in contemporary discussions.

The present paper seeks to address this gap by focusing on schools as key sites where ethically relevant decisions are routinely made. Drawing on Helmut Fend's systematization of formal education (Fend 2008a, 2008b), which distinguishes three levels of education—macro (education policy), meso (actual schools), and micro (teaching)—the focus is placed on the meso-level: schools. The paper explores how schools function as ethical decision-making bodies and identifies the central ethical themes that arise within these institutions. It begins by conceptualizing the ethical responsibilities across all levels of formal education, from policy to classroom practice. It then delves into the role of schools in shaping and making ethical decisions, exploring which choices are (or can be) made at the institutional level. Finally, the paper outlines the ethical responsibilities of schools and underscores their role in shaping the educational experience in a way that is both ethically grounded and socially responsible.

I. Educational Ethics within the Ethical Framework

Ethics should not be reduced to applied ethics; rather, applied ethics—which includes educational ethics—can only be understood within the broader context of ethics (Turnherr, 2000, p. 7). Ethics can be categorized in various ways, and Figure 1 presents one such classification: the distinction made here between philosophical and non-philosophical ethics is based on differing methodological approaches. While both religious and philosophical ethics share the same tasks and objectives, religious ethics do not rely solely on experience and reason to justify their principles. Instead, they may also draw on supernatural sources of knowledge (Morscher, 2012, pp. 54–55).

Despite this methodological difference, moral theology remains significant in the context of educational ethics. Historically, religious moral concepts have played a crucial role in shaping educational systems and the norms and values embedded within them (e.g., Reble, 2004; Seel, 2010; Tenorth, 2010). Furthermore, although Wilhelm von Humboldt (1792/2016) and other philosophers advocated for a clear separation between education and religion, this division has yet to be fully realized in many places.

Fig. 1.: Categorization of Ethics and Embedding of Educational Ethics (Bacher, 2025)

Descriptive ethics, on the other hand, focuses on empirical research on norms and value systems, primarily within the social and cultural sciences. While not a philosophical discipline in a strict methodological sense, it can still contribute significantly to philosophical ethics (von Kutschner, 1999, pp. 42–43) by providing valuable insights and data (Hübner, 2021, p. 24). For example, empirical studies on moral values can inform the development and justification of principles in educational ethics.

As illustrated in Figure 1, philosophical ethics can be divided into three sub-disciplines: (1) metaethics, (2) normative ethics, and (3) applied ethics. These three areas are closely interconnected and build upon one another. Applied ethics applies principles developed within normative ethics, while normative ethics is grounded in metaethics to ensure a consistent justification of its principles. The relations can be expressed as follows:

- (1) Metaethics can be referred to as the theory of science of ethics (Pieper, 2017, p. 73). It serves as the foundation of ethics by seeking to clarify the fundamental status of moral concepts, statements, and arguments, thereby providing the basis for consistent ethical reasoning. Metaethics explores the justification of ethical statements on ontological, epistemological, and linguistic levels. It analyzes the

structure and origins of moral beliefs, aiming to understand what it means to speak of right and wrong, good and bad—without addressing specific moral questions or making normative judgments. (Hübner, 2021, p. 37).

- (2) Normative ethics focuses on evaluating actions in terms of their moral rightness or wrongness and establishing principles that guide moral behavior. It is generally divided into deontic (norm-based) and axiological (value-based) ethics (Morscher, 2012, p. 61). Normative ethics encompasses philosophical theories that establish standards for what ought to be done (Pauer-Studer, 2020, p. 14), as well as what is prohibited, good, or bad. Its primary aim is to formulate well-founded principles for human action and develop approaches for assessing moral dilemmas and decision-making in ethically significant situations.
- (3) Applied ethics (also known as practical ethics) aims to apply principles from normative ethics to concrete issues, providing guidance for decision-making in complex and often controversial areas of human life (Turnherr, 2000, p. 14). According to Morscher (2012), the role of applied ethics is to critically examine various moral positions in light of their theoretical foundations and to establish a consistent, ideally coherent, yet revisable set of moral principles that can serve as a basis for discussion. Classical subfields of applied ethics include medical ethics, business ethics, scientific ethics, and animal ethics. Educational ethics is also part of this domain.

Philosophical ethics provides the ethical framework for multi-perspective reflection and argumentation on education-related ethical issues. However, to identify which themes take center stage, insights from educational sciences are essential. Therefore, the perspective shifts at this point to systematically identifying the key thematic areas of educational ethics.

2. The Thematic Range of (Formal) Educational Education

One effective way to systematize the formal education system is to break it down into different levels, each involving distinct actors who play key roles in shaping the educational landscape (Candia et al. 2023; Fend, 2008a; 2008b; Garira, 2024). This approach provides a solid foundation for structuring educational ethics, as decisions and judgments made at each level often carry significant moral weight (Bacher, 2025). By focusing on the various actors involved at each stage of the educational process, we can better understand how ethics is inherently tied to the decisions being made, bringing us back to the core of ethics itself—the question of what constitutes right and wrong human action.

In this context, I turn to Fend’s multi-level model of formal education (Fend, 2008a; 2008b). He divides the education system into three distinct levels: the macro-level (educational policy), the meso-level (the schools), and the micro-level (teaching). Each of these levels is associated with decision-making processes that involve various actors, and at each level, decisions are made that can have ethical implications for students, teachers, and society at large. This approach serves as a framework for understanding how educational ethics plays a role in guiding these decisions.

Importantly, Fend’s analysis goes beyond simply examining the “is” or “can” states of education (i.e., the current state and potential possibilities of the education system). It also addresses the “should” state—what ought to be the case in terms of moral responsibility. This dimension is at the heart of educational ethics, which is concerned with the values, principles, and ideals that should guide the actions of those involved in the educational process. In other words, it is not only about understanding how education functions or can function, but also about determining how it should function in an ethical, responsible way.

At each level of the system, from policy decisions to classroom practices, different stakeholders—such as policymakers, school administrators, teachers, students, and their caregivers—are involved in making decisions. These decisions, often with profound implications, shape the educational experiences of individuals and influence the broader social and cultural fabric. Therefore, it is essential to recognize the ethical dimensions of decision-making at each of these levels.

Building upon this framework, Figure 2 provides a schematic representation of a categorization of educational ethics, which further illuminates how these different levels intersect and interact in the context of formal education.

Fig. 2: Content-Related Categorization of (Formal) Educational Ethics with Focus on the Meso-Level (Bacher, 2025)

As demonstrated in Figure 2, ethically relevant decisions are made at every level of formal education. At the macro-level, educational policy establishes ethical standards by stipulating the definition of educational goals and content and by shaping the structural design of the educational system. At the meso-level, schools exercise autonomous decision-making that governs the organization of school culture and daily life, thereby embedding ethical practices within the institutional framework. Finally, at the micro-level, teachers make daily ethical decisions and are responsible for ensuring that students receive an education grounded in ethical principles. These layers are intertwined and create a comprehensive approach where ethics is deeply integrated into both policy and practice throughout the educational landscape.

In the following section, the focus will be on the meso-level of (formal) educational ethics.

3. Educational Ethics at the Meso-Level

Institutional structures are flexible and can be shaped (Prenzel, 2020, p. 74). At the meso-level of formal education, as Fend (2008a, 2008b) describes, schools recontextualize the educational frameworks (designed at the macro-level) to fit their local conditions. Thus, decisions are guided by institutional frameworks but are adapted to reflect the unique conditions and needs of each individual school. In doing this, schools have to not only organize classes in terms of time and space, but also tackle a variety of tasks that involve numerous ethically relevant decisions. While traditional models emphasize schools primarily as administrative units executing orders, new approaches compel them to make independent pedagogical and ethical decisions. At the same time, all actions take place within a detailed legal framework structured by formal procedures. This complex task structure illustrates how schools, as corporate actors, implement their institutional mandates into a living school development. The key actors at the meso-level are school principals or school leadership teams, school quality assurance officers, teachers, students, and students' guardians.

The role of educational ethics at the meso-level is to ensure that school-autonomous decisions are made transparently, are understandable, and are based on sound reasoning within the specific context of each school. This means that schools must engage in ethical reflection to ensure that their decisions contribute to a positive and inclusive educational environment. Furthermore, creating a “good” (a concept fundamentally rooted in ethics) school environment involves addressing ethical questions that are deeply intertwined with values and principles, including how schools respond to changing societal values (Gardner, 2006; Zecha, 2018). Therefore, a thoughtful ethical approach in shaping school life is vital for maintaining the quality of education and fostering a positive atmosphere for all members of the school community.

The meso-level encompasses school policy, leadership, development, community engagement, and school culture (Fend, 2008a, p. 17). It is structured by autonomy rules and leadership regulations. As a result, decisions at this level—including those with ethical implications—primarily focus on (1) school-autonomous decision-making and (2) organizing of school culture and school life.

3.1. Developing School-autonomous Decision Guidelines

Western European schools have increasingly been granted significant autonomy in decision-making over the last years (Christ & Dobbins, 2016; Directorate-General for Education, 2008; Fend, 2008a), but what does this autonomy truly entail in practice? At its core, the concept of school autonomy raises ethical questions about the authority behind decision-making, the principles that should guide these decisions, and the processes by which they are made. Who, ultimately, should hold the power to make decisions within a school, and on what basis should these decisions be grounded? Are decisions to be guided solely by operational needs and logistical concerns, or should they be influenced by broader ethical frameworks? These are fundamental questions that must be addressed when considering the nature of autonomous decision-making in schools.

One key element in understanding school autonomy is the recognition that decisions can be shaped by specific guiding principles, such as a school's mission statement or its focus areas. These guiding principles often reflect a deeper ethical vision, rooted in a normative understanding of education and the role of schools in society. School values are not just abstract ideals but serve as the foundation for the decision-making process at all levels of the school (Fend, 2008a). For instance, the distinct school type of (Accredited) European Schools (Office of the Secretary-General of the European Schools, 2025) incorporates a key element known as the European dimension, which encompasses a set of core values, including respect for other cultures, tolerance, peace, democracy, and solidarity (Silian, 2024, p. 150). Although these values are often established at the macro-level, their realization depends fundamentally on meso-level implementation. When decisions are made in alignment with these principles, the autonomy of the school is not merely operational but is also infused with a deeper ethical commitment to shaping students' development and well-being.

The autonomy of schools allows them to make decisions in a variety of areas, depending on the type of school and the legal regulations that govern them. Depending on the respective education system, school autonomy varies. For instance, in Austria, as of 2025, school autonomy encompasses a range of decisions, including curriculum adaptations, organization of instruction (such as class structuring, group arrangements, and lesson scheduling), experimental school projects (which may involve implementation and collaboration with external school partners), school hours (including school-free days, whether Saturday is considered a school day, the start and end times of school periods, and supervision policies), and the implementation of full-day school models. In addition to these areas, schools have the authority to make decisions regarding staff selection and development, school partnerships, and collaboration with other educational institutions (BMBWF, 2018).

When schools are viewed as corporate actors (Fend, 2008a), school leadership assumes a central role. The principal holds primary responsibility for implementing legal requirements and shaping the school both administratively and pedagogically—especially within the framework of growing autonomy. This so-called recontextualization task demands not only leadership skills but also the ability to collaborate, emotional intelligence, and a strong sense for pedagogical development. Effective school leadership (MacBeath, 1998; Browne, 2021) means guiding the school in dialogue with the teaching staff, encouraging participation in decision-making, fostering a positive

school climate, and striking a balance between adherence to regulations and openness to innovation. The quality of leadership is especially reflected in how it is perceived by the staff—as involving trust, oversight, humor, openness to new ideas, and the capacity for constructive communication and problem-solving. While fulfilling formal duties is expected, it is attributes like confidence, fairness, integrity, and a forward-thinking mindset that truly define strong leadership. Good school leadership inspires, motivates, and creates a shared sense of responsibility for a vibrant and future-oriented school.

In the spirit of inclusion and participation, it is often emphasized that school-autonomous decisions should be made with input from a broad range of stakeholders within the school community (Solhaug, 2018; Williams, 1989). This could involve teachers, students, parents, and administrative staff, all of whom bring different perspectives and experiences to the decision-making table. Democratic voting processes are one way to engage the community in school-level decisions, ensuring that the voices of all those affected by these decisions are heard and considered. These participatory processes not only foster a sense of ownership and accountability among stakeholders, but also enhance the legitimacy of the decisions made. However, this approach touches on the broader issue of who is considered a legitimate participant in shaping the direction of a school and the ethical implications of such inclusion.

Moreover, school autonomy is not universally viewed as positive. It is linked to neoliberal trends in education, as increased school autonomy may foster a more competitive environment among schools (Niesche & Thomson, 2017). Wermke and Solokangas (2021) examined teachers' perceptions of professional autonomy in Finland, Ireland, Germany, and Sweden, finding that increased autonomy does not necessarily correlate with improved outcomes. Instead, it can increase complexity, pressure, and anxiety, sometimes causing teachers to resist autonomy. This insight, termed the “autonomy paradox,” challenges the common belief that more autonomy is always beneficial. Furthermore, Sholderer et al. (2017) found that school autonomy improves performance in countries with high social capital but can harm performance in countries with lower social capital. This suggests that the effectiveness of granting schools more decision-making power depends on the surrounding social environment, highlighting the need for tailored educational reforms.

Thus, the process by which decisions are made within schools requires careful consideration. Schratz (2003) argues that it is vital for school organizational structures to be transparent, flexible, and responsive to the specific needs and conditions of the school community. These structures must be clearly documented and should facilitate efficient decision-making processes that align with the educational mandate of the institution. Schools should be able to clearly communicate how decisions are made, who is responsible for making them, and the rationale behind these decisions. Transparency not only builds trust within the school community but also ensures that decisions are made in a fair and accountable manner. At the same time, the structures must be designed to be adaptable, allowing schools to respond to changes in the local context, evolving educational needs, and emerging challenges.

In order to foster an environment conducive to pedagogical development, it is essential that the focus of decision-making be on the needs of students, particularly their learning, rather than solely on the logistics of teaching (Schratz, 2018). Pedagogical school development should center on the

improvement of learning processes, aiming to create an environment that nurtures intellectual curiosity, critical thinking, and personal growth. It is not enough to focus on improving teaching methods or expanding curricula; schools must also consider how to create an environment that supports students' emotional and social development. By placing learning at the heart of decision-making, schools can ensure that their autonomous decisions contribute not only to operational efficiency but also to the overall educational experience and well-being of students.

This underscores how complex decision-making can be in autonomous schools. Clear and transparent guidelines are essential, but they must also remain flexible to address the unique needs of each school community. This is why it is especially important that such decisions are rooted in strong ethical principles. When grounded in ethics, school autonomy becomes more than just an administrative tool—it reflects the school's values and its commitment.

3.2. Shaping School Life

The way schools design their environments reflects their deeper guiding principles and (implicit) moral beliefs. The organization of school culture and school life is a deeply ethical undertaking, as the well-being, personal development, and overall happiness of both students (Konu & Rimpelä, 2002) and teachers (Viac & Fraser, 2020) are profoundly influenced by the way schools structure their environments and activities. School life is not merely a backdrop to academic instruction; it plays a central role in shaping the lives of everyone involved. As Heis and Mascotti-Knoflach (2022) point out, schools are places of growth, offering not only intellectual education but also emotional, social, and ethical development. These factors make the shaping of school life a complex and significant process, demanding careful ethical reflection on the values and principles that should guide every aspect of it.

The implementation of institutional guidelines and the shaping of school life at the level of individual schools necessitate numerous ethically relevant decisions. As schools gain more autonomy, their responsibility increases because they are required to make decisions that often involve significant ethical considerations. The process of developing a school in an ethically responsible manner must be driven by the schools themselves, with careful reflection on the ethical dimensions of each choice (Wiesner & Schreiner, 2021).

The establishment of curricular and didactic priorities at a school raises further ethical questions about what is taught, how it is taught, and the purpose of education itself. Schools must decide which subjects or topics take priority in their curricula and how to approach the teaching of these subjects. These decisions are not neutral but are infused with values—values about what knowledge is most important, what skills are most necessary for students to acquire, and what it means to lead a fulfilling life. Whether a school emphasizes scientific literacy, social-emotional learning, or the arts, each decision reflects an underlying belief about the goals of education and its role in shaping individuals and society. These curricular and extracurricular choices carry ethical implications, as they influence not only what students learn but how they learn to think, engage with the world, and relate to others.

According to Altrichter et al. (2016), key elements that contribute to the quality of a school extend far beyond the realm of subject-specific instruction. These elements include opportunities for

personal development in various spheres, such as cultural, social, and athletic activities. Personal development, in this sense, refers to the holistic growth of students as individuals—developing their creativity, social skills, athletic abilities, and emotional intelligence. Schools that provide rich opportunities for such development foster well-rounded individuals who are prepared not only academically but also socially and emotionally for the challenges they will face in life. The process of establishing school-specific priorities is not limited to academic and performance-oriented decisions but also encompasses aspects related to school life, such as organizing celebrations and fostering a positive school culture (Weinert, 2000, p. 10).

Schools are often viewed as living spaces where extracurricular activities make a significant contribution to the quality of childhood and adolescent experiences (Dewey, 1916; Fend, 2008a; von Hentig, 2007). The inclusion of extracurricular activities—whether in the arts, sports, or community service—serves to enrich students’ lives and provide them with avenues to explore their interests and passions. These opportunities contribute to the creation of a school culture that values and supports the full spectrum of human potential. Good schools offer a variety of positively valued events (e.g., festivals, concerts, parental involvement) that foster staff engagement and social integration, whereas underperforming schools often exhibit a negative attitude and lower participation. Vibrant school events substantially contribute to educational effectiveness by making the “hidden” educational spirit visible and tangible.

In this context, schools play an essential role in fostering a sense of community (Sergiovanni, 1994) and social integration. Schools should not only be places of individual growth but also spaces where students, teachers, and staff interact and collaborate in ways that promote a sense of belonging and mutual respect. A strong, inclusive community within the school is crucial for creating an environment in which students feel safe, supported, and understood. Schools should make conscious efforts to recognize and value diversity in all its forms and work to ensure that every student, regardless of background, feels respected and included. Additionally, schools should develop transparent strategies for addressing and resolving conflicts constructively (Harris & Morrisson, 2013). Conflict is inevitable in any community, but how it is managed can determine the health and success of the school environment. It is important for schools to cultivate an atmosphere where disagreements are handled respectfully, where individuals can express differing opinions without fear of retaliation, and where all parties are encouraged to work together toward peaceful solutions.

One of the most significant tensions in shaping school life is the balance between freedom and regulation (Fend, 2008a; Havinghurst, 1973). On the one hand, schools must create rules that enable a harmonious and non-violent coexistence among students and staff. These rules are necessary to establish order, promote fairness, and ensure that everyone in the school community can engage in their work and activities in a safe and supportive environment. On the other hand, schools must be cautious not to impose excessive restrictions on individual freedoms. Education is not merely about following rules but about empowering students to think critically, make their own decisions, and develop into independent, responsible individuals. Overly restrictive rules can stifle students’ autonomy and creativity, limiting their ability to grow and learn in ways that are meaningful to them. Thus, schools must carefully consider the types of rules and regulations they implement, ensuring that these rules strike a balance between providing structure and respecting individual rights.

In this context, rules and rituals serve as essential tools for fostering a democratic school culture. They provide guidance and structure, helping students understand how to interact with others respectfully and responsibly. The goal is to create a school environment where everyone—students, teachers, staff, and parents—feels part of a shared mission to foster mutual respect and democratic values. Prengel (1999) emphasizes that these rules and rituals should support democratic community life and promote mutual respect. They should encourage students to consider the needs and perspectives of others, to engage in dialogue, and to contribute to the collective well-being of the school community. In this way, the shaping of school life becomes an ethical endeavor that goes beyond administrative tasks to encompass the very values that a school seeks to impart to its students.

The design of school life involves a complex interplay of values, principles, and practical considerations. By carefully considering these ethical dimensions, schools can create environments that not only promote academic achievement but also nurture the personal and social growth of students, preparing them to become ethically responsible members of society.

Conclusion and Outlook

Schools are not merely sites of knowledge transmission; they are ethical communities that shape the lives of future generations. As this paper has argued, recognizing schools as ethical decision-makers at the meso-level of the education system is crucial for understanding the value-laden nature of educational practices and institutional life. By drawing on philosophical ethics and educational science, this paper has demonstrated that the decisions made at the meso-level are not simply technical or administrative but deeply normative. Given the multifaceted nature of educational ethics, an interdisciplinary approach is essential to effectively addressing the complex ethical issues that schools encounter daily. Bridging philosophical ethics and educational science offers valuable insights for navigating the ethical dimensions of school governance and practice. The complexity of educational ethics at the meso-level is illustrated in Figure 3, which categorizes various elements of this field and emphasizes its importance in understanding and guiding school decision-making.

The increasing autonomy of schools within many educational systems presents both opportunities and ethical responsibilities. It requires schools to reflect on the values guiding their decisions, to involve diverse stakeholders in shaping school life, and to prioritize the well-being and development of students. At the meso-level, educational ethics plays a central role in guiding school-autonomous decisions to be transparent, well-reasoned, and aligned with the core values and mission of the institution. As societal values continue to evolve, schools must engage in ongoing ethical reflection, adapting to new challenges while maintaining their ethical integrity. Shaping school culture and everyday school life is also an ethically charged endeavor, requiring careful consideration of how policies and practices impact the students and communities they serve.

Looking ahead, ethical foundations as well as the development of robust frameworks for educational ethics at the meso-level are essential. In an era of rapid change, educational institutions will need to rethink their approaches to ethical decision-making in response to new societal challenges. Schools must continue to develop strategies that allow them to act as ethical

decision-makers, balancing the pressures of educational policy, societal expectations, and the ever-changing needs of students.

It will be essential to deepen the discussion on ethical decision-making in schools by involving all stakeholders—teachers, students, guardians, and policymakers. By fostering a culture of ethical reflection and collaboration, schools can build stronger, more resilient educational environments that better prepare students to thrive in an increasingly complex world. Educational ethics at the meso-level will remain a vital field of inquiry, guiding schools in their mission to nurture future generations. Through ongoing engagement with ethical challenges, schools can ensure that their decisions promote not only academic success but also holistic growth and the well-being of all members of the school community.

Fig. 3: Categorization of (Formal) Educational Ethics within Ethics with Focus on the Meso-Level (Bacher, 2025)

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